

ABSTRACT

Graph theory is widely used to prove many mathematical theorems and models. This paper presents the various techniques of semi-regular graphs to solve problems in different fields of technology in addition to mathematics. Graph theory is nothing but a branch of discrete mathematics. Graph theory is a study of graphs which are mathematical structures not only used in computer science but in many fields. Two problem areas are mainly considered. Problems such as classical problems and problems from an application. The problems from an application focus on experimental research and implementation construction of semi-regular graphs. Graphs are important because they are a way of expressing information in pictorial form. A graph shows information that equivalent to many words. Many problems that are difficult to determine or implement can easily be solved by graphic theory. There are many types of graphs as part of graph theory. Each type of graph is related to a particular property. One of these graphs is used in many troubleshooting applications. Because of the representation of power of graphs and flexibility, many problems can be represented and solved easily. So by studying various papers on semi-regular graphs. In this paper, some special graphs have been identified as semi-regular graphs, and their properties have also been discussed. We have described the various classes of semi-regular graphs and also discussed the properties of semi-regular graphs. And also the Construction of semi-regular. We can actually discuss Distance symmetry, $k_2 + n$ and $k_n + 1$. And working on these Semi-regular graphs.

Keywords: Regular graph, Semi-regular graph, Distance symmetric, barbell graph, Circulant graph, and vertex-transitive.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

Symbols	Nomenclature
\leq	Less then or equal to
\geq	Greater or equal
\neq	not equal to
\in	Belongs to

LIST OF ABBREVIATION

Abbreviation	Description
deg	degree
K_n	complete graph
P_n	path
C_n	cycle
cir	circulant graph
mod	modulus
G^c	complement of the graph

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Graph theory is a branch of mathematics that has undergone many developments. There are many topics studied in graph theory, one of which is semi-regular graphs. The term “semi-regular graph” was coined by Coxeter in 1937, and since then, numerous authors have contributed to the understanding of this class of graphs. The study of semi-regular graphs has gained attention in the field of graph theory due to their interesting properties and applications in various areas such as network design, coding theory, and combinatorial optimization. Semi-regular graphs have been studied initially in the form of combination graphs (Balaban, 1972) and convolution graphs (Kerek, 1974). The study of semi-regular graphs got much attention from graph theorists only after the publication of the paper ‘Distance degree regular graphs’ by Bloom G.S. and others (1981). Alison Northup (2002) described various classes of semi-regular graphs and also discussed an algorithm for determining semi-regular graphs. Inspired by these works in this paper we have determined as Construction of semi-regular graphs. In this paper, some graphs have been identified as semi-regular graphs and their properties have also been discussed. We have described the various classes of semi-regular graphs, and also the construction of semi-regular graphs and Distance symmetric from some special graphs.

1.2 literature Review

The review of the literature helps to understand my research topic, I have collected some important information from numerous publications by some researchers on the topic of my research which are listed below. The thesis has been split up into five parts.

P.Erdos, L.Szekely and W.T.Trotter have shown the existence of infinitely many K_3 -irregular graphs, while it was shown that k_n -irregular graphs exist for every $n \geq 3$. we believe that F-irregular graphs exist for every connected graph F with at least three vertices .

C.W.Evans introduced Semi-regular graphs that have been applied to chemistry by Balaban and Kerek in the form of combination graphs and convolution graphs.

N.Murugas and R. Anitha investigated and discussed what characteristics semi-regular graphs have in common. They have defined the circulant graph and examined their semi-regularity.

Medha Itagi Huilgol in this paper they present an exhaustive review of the two concepts of DDR and DDI graphs. The paper starts with an insight into all distance-related sequences and their applications.

Alison Northup Describe how the property of semi-regularity relates to other properties of graphs,such as regularity, vertex-transitivity and symmetry. the semi-regular trees are fully classified. In addition, an algorithm for determining whether a graph is semi-regular is presented.

M.Sakthi in this paper it is discussed the relationship between distance and domination. And also explained some concepts for domination with domination numbers using the wiener index and domination matrix based on distance.

N.R.Santhi Maheswari and C Sekar in this paper includes the existence of some $(r,2,k)$ - regular graphs and a few examples of $(2,k)$ regular graphs and also study some graph products in $(2,k)$ regular and $(r,2,k)$ regular graph.

N.R. Santhi Maheswari and C.Sekar in this paper, we consider only finite, simple, connected graphs. We denote the vertex set and edge set of a graph G by $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ respectively. The degree of a vertex v is the number of edges incident at v . A graph G is regular if all its vertices have the same degree.

1.3 Detailed of the Thesis Statement

The thesis has been split up into five parts. In the first chapter, I have given the introduction, Literature Review in which I have stated various ideas I have got from these papers and the detailed structure of the thesis statement.

In the second Chapter, I have introduced some fundamental graph theoretical definitions to understand the following chapters fully.

In the third chapter, I have derived some properties of semi-regular graphs and discussed them, along with some graphs Semi-regular graphs such as Wagner, path, cycle, and complete. Further, we discussed the 0-semi-regular graph and 1-semi-regular graph.

In the fourth chapter, I have derived the construction of semi-regular graphs and discussed them, along with the construction of graphs such as barbell graphs, circulant graphs, and vertex-transitive graphs. Further, we discussed whether the Semi-regular graphs are distance symmetric or not.

In the last chapter, I provided my research conclusion at the end of the paper, along with a suggestion for how I might modify it in various ways.

CHAPTER 2

PRELIMINARY

2.1 Introduction

Before getting to my topic, it is crucial for the further development of my paper that we understand some fundamental definitions and notions of the vocabulary employed. To help users receive the information they need, I have added some definitions below.

2.2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.2.1

The number of edges incident on a vertex V_i , with self-loop counted twice is called a degree of vertex V_i .

Figure 1: Degree of vertex

Definition 2.2.2

Let G be a simple graph. The complement G^c of G is another graph with the same vertex set $V(G)$ and two vertices are adjacent in G^c if they are not adjacent in G .

Figure 2: Complement of a graph

Definition 2.2.3

A graph is said to be regular if every vertex in the graph has the same degree. If all the vertices of a graph have degree n then the graph is called n -regular graph.

Figure 3: Regular Graph

Definition 2.2.4

A complete graph is a graph in which each vertex is connected to every other vertex.

Figure 4: Complete graph

Definition 2.2.5

Let G be any graph. An alternating sequence of vertices and edges starting with a vertex and ending with a vertex and is such that every edge in the sequence is incident on the preceding and succeeding vertices is called a walk in the graph. It may be denoted by W .

Figure 5: Walk

Definition 2.2.6

A walk is called a path if all its points are distinct.

Figure 6: Path

Definition 2.2.7

A walk is called trail if its edges are distinct.

Figure 7: Trail

Definition 2.2.8

A closed walk in which no vertex appears more than once is called a circuit. That is a circuit is a closed. A cycle of length k is called k -cycle. The number of edges in a cycle is called the length of cycle. If the length of the cycle is odd number then the cycle is called odd cycle otherwise it is even cycle.

Figure 8: Cycle

Definition 2.2.9

Let r_1, r_2, \dots, r_k be the reduced residue system modulo m . A graph G with vertex set $\{v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{m-1}\}$ in which v_i is adjacent to v_j if and only if $i - j \pmod{m} = r \cdot n$, for some n satisfying $1 \leq n \leq k$, is called circulant graph corresponding to the integer m . It is denoted as $\text{cir}(m)$.

Definition 2.2.10

A graph G is vertex-transitive if for every pair of vertices v_i and v_j in G there is an automorphism on G mapping v_i to v_j . It can be easily seen that every one-one and onto mapping defined on the set of vertices of a complete graph to itself is an automorphism.

CHAPTER 3

SOME PROPERTIES OF SEMI-REGULAR GRAPHS

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the notion of the some properties of semi regular graphs is introduced and discussed, along with the some graphs is Semi-regular graphs such as Wagner, path, cycle and complete. Further we discussed the 0-semi-regular graph and 1-semi-regular graph.

3.2 Main Result

Definition 3.2.1

A graph is said to be semi-regular if each vertex in the graph is distance 2 away from exactly the same number of vertices. If each vertex is distance 2 from n other vertices then the graph is called an n -semi-regular graph.

Figure 9: n -semi-regular graphs

Example 3.2.2

To prove the Wagner graph is a 4-semi-regular graph.

Figure 10: Wagner

vertices	vertices at distance 2
v_1	v_3, v_4, v_6, v_9
v_2	v_4, v_5, v_7, v_8
v_3	v_1, v_5, v_6, v_8
v_4	v_1, v_2, v_6, v_7
v_5	v_2, v_3, v_7, v_8
v_6	v_1, v_3, v_4, v_8
v_7	v_1, v_2, v_4, v_5
v_8	v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6

Table 1: Wagner graph

Theorem 3.2.3

A Connected graph is 0-semi-regular if and only if it is a complete graph k_n for $n \geq 1$.

Proof:

Let G be a connected 0-semi-regular graph with n vertices $n \geq 1$. The

Distance between any two vertices of G must be ≤ 1 , because a distance greater than 1 would mean that they were distance 2 apart. If G would therefore not be 0-semi-regular. A connected graph with n vertices in which all vertices are at distance 1 from all other vertices is the complete graph K_n . Let G be the complete graph K_n for $n \geq 1$. Then for any vertex v in G , v is not distance 2 away from any other vertices. Thus, G is 0-semi-regular.

Theorem 3.2.4

Let G be a semi-regular graph and let u and v be any two vertices of degree m . If there is a vertex x of degree n adjacent to u then there is a vertex y of degree n , adjacent to the vertex v .

Proof:

Let G be a semi-regular graph. Let $\deg u = \deg v = m$. Also, let x and y be vertices adjacent to u and v respectively, such that $\deg x = k$ and $\deg y = l$ where $k \neq l$.

For simplicity, first let us assume that $\deg u = \deg v = 1$.

Then if $\deg x \neq \deg y$, then the number of vertices which are at distance 2 from u and v will not be the same. It is a contradiction to the assumption that G is semi-regular.

Next let us assume that $\deg u = \deg v \geq 1$, then the number of vertices which are at distance 2 to u through the vertex x is k .

Similarly the number of vertices which are at distance 2 to v through y is l . Since $k \neq l$, the number of vertices which are at distance 2 from u and v are not the same.

Again this is a contradiction, Hence the Theorem. Thus S is Semi-regular.

Theorem 3.2.5

If a graph G is semi-regular then given any vertex u of deg m , the sum of degrees of adjacent vertices is a constant, independent of the choice of u .

Proof:

Let G be a Semi-regular graph.

Let u and v be any two vertices in G .

Such that $\deg(u) = \deg(v)$.

From the above theorem, both the vertices u and v will have adjacent vertices of the same degrees.

Hence the sum of the degrees of adjacent vertices of u and v is a constant.

Illustration

Figure 11: 4-semi-regular

The following table gives the sum of the degree of adjacent vertices in Figure 3.

vertices of deg 1	Adjacent vertices	Sum of degrees of adjacent vertices
v_7	v_4	5
v_8	v_6	5
v_9	v_1	5
v_{10}	v_3	5

vertices of deg 2	Adjacent vertices	Sum of degrees of adjacent vertices
v_2	v_1, v_4	10
v_5	v_3, v_6	10

vertices of deg 5	Adjacent vertices	Sum of degrees of adjacent vertices
v_1	v_9, v_2, v_4, v_6, v_3	18
v_3	$v_{10}, v_4, v_5, v_6, v_1$	18
v_4	v_1, v_2, v_3, v_6, v_7	18
v_6	v_1, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_8	18

Table 2: Sum of degrees of vertices

Theorem 3.2.6

Every finite 1- semi-regular has an even number of vertices.

Proof:

Let G be a 1- semi-regular graph.

Let v be a vertex of G .

since G is 1- semi-regular, v must be distance 2 away from exactly one other vertex in G .

u is distance 2 away from v alone.

Thus the vertices of G can be divided into pairs that are distance 2 away from each other, but not from any other vertex.

If G had an odd number of vertices, there would be a vertex that was not part of a pair.

Therefore not distance 2 away from any other vertex.

then G would not be 1- semi-regular.

So G must have an even number of vertices

Lemma 3.2.7

The Smallest 1- Semi-regular graph is P_4

Proof:

Let G be a 1- semi-regular graph.

by theorem, G would even number of vertices.

a graph with 2 vertices cannot be 1- semi-regular.

consider the graph with 4 vertices namely v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 .

Suppose v_1 is at distance 2 from v_3 then v_3 is also at distance 2 from v_1

either v_2 or v_4 should be adjacent to both v_1 and v_3 .

if v_2 is adjacent to v_1 and v_3 then v_4 should be joined only with either v_1 or v_3 but not with v_2 .

Hence v_4 should be adjacent to either v_1 or v_3 .

The graph P_4 is 1- Semi-regular.

Illustration

Figure 12: P_4

The graph P_4 is 1- semi-regular.

Lemma 3.2.8

The Smallest 1- Semi-regular graph is C_4

Proof:

Let G be a 1- semi-regular graph.

by theorem, G would even number of vertices.

a graph with 2 vertices cannot be 1- semi-regular.

consider the graph with 4 vertices namely v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4 .

Suppose v_1 is at distance 2 from v_3 then v_3 is also at distance 2 from v_1
both v_2 and v_4 should be adjacent to both v_1 and v_3 .

if v_2 is adjacent to v_1 and v_3 then v_4 should be joined only with both v_1 and v_3
but not with v_2 .

Hence v_4 should be adjacent to both v_1 and v_3 .

The graph C_4 is 1- semi-regular.

Illustration

Figure 13: C_4

The graph C_4 is 1- semi-regular.

CHAPTER 4

CONSTRUCTION OF SEMI-REGULAR GRAPHS

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the notion of the construction of semi-regular graphs is introduced and discussed, along with the construction of graphs such as barbell graphs, circulant graphs, and vertex transitive graphs. Further we discussed the Semi-regular graphs is distance symmetric or not.

4.2 Main Result

Definition 4.2.1

If the set of vertices can be partitioned in terms of vertices of Distance 2 is called Distance Symmetric.

Examples 4.2.2

consider the following semi-regular graphs.

Figure 14: 2-semi-regular(G_1) and 3-semiregular(G_2)

vertex(V)	vertices at distance 2 from V in (G_1)
v_1	v_3, v_4
v_2	v_4, v_6
v_3	v_1, v_5
v_4	v_2, v_6
v_5	v_1, v_3
v_6	v_2, v_4

vertex(V)	vertices at distance 2 from V in (G_2)
v_1	v_3, v_4, v_7
v_2	v_5, v_6, v_8
v_3	v_1, v_4, v_8
v_4	v_1, v_3, v_8
v_5	v_2, v_6, v_7
v_6	v_2, v_5, v_7
v_7	v_1, v_5, v_6
v_8	v_2, v_3, v_4

Table 3: Distance symmetric

From the above table it can be seen that the 2-semi-regular graph G_1 is distance symmetric because the vertex set can be partitioned into two sets $A = \{v_1, v_3, v_5\}$; $B = \{v_2, v_4, v_6\}$ in terms of vertices of distance 2. But the 3-semi-regular graph G_2 is not distance symmetric as it can be seen that the vertex set cannot be partitioned into subsets of the vertex set of G_2 in terms of distance 2.

Definition 4.2.3

The graph constructed from k_2 by adding n pendent vertices each at both the vertices of k_2 is called n -barbell graph. It is denoted as $k_2 + n$.

Theorem 4.2.4

The graph obtained from the complete graph K_2 by adding n equal number of pendent vertices at both vertices of K_2 is an n -semi-regular graph. The n -semi-regular graph so obtained has $2n+2$ vertices and $2n+1$ edges.

Proof:

Figure 15: n - Barbell Graphs

Theorem 4.2.5

The n -Barbell graph is n -semi regular and also distance symmetric.

Proof:

Let G be the n -barbell graph. That is, G is formed by a central line segment connecting u and v with n other vertices connected to each of u and v . Let v be a vertex in G . For $n = 0$, G is 0-semi-regular. For all other n , there are two possible cases.

Case 1: v is a point on the central line segment of G . There are $n+1$ vertices

connected to v , including u . There are also n other vertices connected to u , and v is distance 2 from each of them. We have considered all the vertices of G , so $\deg_2(v) = n$.

Case 2: v is an endpoint of G . v is distance 2 from u and the other $n-1$ other vertices connected onto v . v is distance 3 from the n vertices connected onto u . We have considered all the vertices of G , so $\deg_2(v) = (n-1)+1 = n$. Thus, $\deg_2(v) = n$ for every vertex v in G , and G is n -semi-regular. The proof is in a simple way as follows

Let $V(K_2)=u,v$; Also let $K_2(n)$ is the graph obtained by adding the pendent vertices w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n at u , and w_{n+1}, \dots, w_{2n} at v . The following table gives the vertices which are at distance 2 from the given vertex.

vertex	vertices which are distance 2
u	w_{n+1}, \dots, w_{2n}
v	w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n
$w_i, i=1, 2, \dots, n$	$v, w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{i-1}, w_{i+1}, \dots, w_n$
$w_{n+i}, i=1, 2, \dots, n$	$u, w_{n+1}, \dots, w_{n+i-1}, \dots, w_{2n}$

Table 4: Barbell graph and distance symmetric

Hence every vertex has exactly n vertices at distance 2. Therefore $K_2(n)$ is an n -semi-regular graph. Also $V(K_2(n))$ can be partitioned into two sets of vertices $A = \{u, w_{n+1}, \dots, w_{2n}\}$ and $B = \{v, w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$. Thus $K_2(n)$ is distance symmetric.

Corollary 4.2.6

The Graphs 0-semi-regular and 1-semi-regular are distance symmetric or not.

Proof:

From a given complete graph, a semi-regular graph can be constructed, and such a graph is not distance symmetric because the vertices which are at distance 2 for a given vertex are always adjacent vertices.

Definition 4.2.7

Let k_n be a complete graph. The graph obtained from k_n by adding pendent vertices at each vertex of k_n is called as $k_n + 1$.

Examples 4.2.8

The complete graph k_3 and k_4 .

Figure 16: $k_n + 1$

Theorem 4.2.9

An $n-1$ semi-regular graph with $2n$ vertices can be constructed from K_n by adding pendent vertices at each vertex of K_n .

Proof:

Consider a complete graph K_n , with vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n . Add the pendent vertices v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n respectively at u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n . It can be seen that for every vertex u_i , the $(n-1)$ vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{(i-1)}, v_{(i+1)}, \dots, v_n$ are at distance 2.

Similarly, Let $d(v_i, v_j) = 1, 1 \leq i \neq j \leq n$.

Let $v_{n+1}, v_{n+2}, \dots, v_{2n}$ are the pendent vertices added respectively at v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n . Then for every vertex $v_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, the vertices $v_{n+1}, v_{n+2}, \dots, v_{n+i-1}, v_{n+i+1}, \dots, v_{2n}$ are at distance 2 and also for every other vertex $v_i, i = n+1, \dots, 2n$, the vertices $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{i-1}, v_{i+1}, \dots, v_n$ are at distance 2. Hence the new graph is an $(n-1)$ semi-regular.

Theorem 4.2.10

For any bijection map $f:V(K'_n)\rightarrow V(K''_n)$ the graph $K'_n f K''_n$ is $(n-1)$ - semi-regular.

Proof:

Let $V(K'_n)=\{u_1,u_2,\dots u_n\}$ and $V(K''_n)=\{v_1,v_2,\dots v_n\}$.

Let $f:V(K'_n)\rightarrow V(K''_n)$ is bijection. Note that no vertex u_i is at distance 2 to any vertex in K_n similarly no vertex v_i is at distance 2 to any vertex in K_n . Also for every vertex u_i in K_n there is exactly one vertex v_i in K_n is adjacent to u_i , by means of an edge added with respect to the bijective map f . i.e., for each vertex u_i except $f(u_i)$, all other vertices in K''_n are at distance 2. The same argument is also applicable to all other vertices in K_n , and also all the vertices in K_n . Hence $K'_n f K''_n$ is $(n-1)$ -semi-regular.

Examples 4.2.11

Figure 17: $K'_n f K''_n$

Theorem 4.2.12

The circulant graph $\text{cir}(p)$, p is a prime is 0-semi-regular.

Proof:

Let p be a prime. The integers relatively prime to p are $1,2,3,\dots p-1$.

Let the vertex set be $\{v_0, v_1,v_2,\dots v_{p-1}\}$. Then for any two integers i,j satisfying $0\leq i, j \leq p-1$, $i-j(\text{mod } p) = r \in 1,2,\dots p-1$.

Hence every v_i is adjacent to v_j . i.e., the circulant graph $\text{cir}(p)$ is a complete graph and hence it is 0-semi-regular.

Figure 18: $\text{cir}(7)$ and $\text{cir}(8)$

Theorem 4.2.13

Let m be an even integer, then the circulant graph $\text{cir}(m)$ is $((m-2)/2)$ -semi-regular.

Proof:

It is clear that v_i, v_{i+1} are always adjacent in a circulant graph $\text{cir}(m)$, for any integer m . Suppose, if m is an even integer then v_i and v_j are at distance 2 to each other, when $i-j$ is even integer. Hence if v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{m-1} are the vertices in $\text{cir}(m)$, then v_0, v_2, \dots, v_{m-2} are at distance 2 to each other and v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{m-1} are also at distance 2 to each other. i.e., each vertex has exactly $((m-2)/2)$ vertices at distance 2 in $\text{cir}(m)$, when m is even. Hence $\text{cir}(m)$, when m is even is $((m-2)/2)$ -semi-regular. Hence the theorem.

Theorem 4.2.14

Every connected vertex-transitive graph is n -semi-regular.

Proof:

Let G be a connected vertex-transitive graph. Let v_1 and v_2 be any two vertices in G . Also let there be n vertices u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n in G .

such that $d(v_i, u_i) = 2$. Then there are 'n' numbers of (v_i, u_i) -paths each of length 2 in G . Let f be an automorphism on G mapping v_1 to v_2 . There are n number of $(v_2, f(u_i))$ -paths, and of length 2. Hence, there are n vertices w_1, \dots, w_n such that $f(u_i) = w_i$, and all w's are exactly two distances away from v_2 . i.e., there are exactly n vertices at distance 2 from v_2 . Hence G is n-semi-regular.

Theorem 4.2.15

If G is an n-semi regular graph, let G^* be defined as the graph with the same vertex set as G , such that v_1 and v_2 are connected in G^* if and only if they are distance 2 away from each other in G . Then G^* is n-regular.

Proof:

Let G be an n-semi regular graph. Let v be a vertex in G . v is then distance 2 away from exactly other vertices in G . Now consider v in G^* . In G^* , v is connected to exactly those vertices that it was distance 2 away from in G . That is, v is connected to exactly n other vertices. Since this is true for all vertices, G^* is n-regular.

Figure 19: a graph G and the corresponding G^*

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

5.1 Conclusion

In this paper, I have introduced the notion of the construction of semi-regular graphs. Also, I have derived the properties of semi-regular graphs. Further, we discussed and studied circulant graphs, vertex-transitive graphs, Barbell graphs, and some more graphs. I have verified the graphs through examples.

5.2 Future Scope

For the Continuation of this project work, the researchers can define Some properties of $1/3$ - regular graphs and construction of $1/3$ - regular graphs. and they can develop their research work to prove the theorem based on Some properties of $1/3$ - regular graphs and construction of $1/3$ - regular graphs.

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